
Plan Overview

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

Title: EcoRPCchem

Creator: Elena Giglia

Principal Investigator: Luca Quaglia

Data Manager: Luca Quaglia

Project Administrator: Luca Quaglia

Affiliation: Other

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ORCID iD: 0000-0002-0793-8275

Project abstract:

With the enforcement of EU regulations 2024/573, the production and usage of Tetrafluoroethane (R134a) has been strongly regulated. This gas is a key component in the gas mixture of Resistive Plate Chambers, a detector technology widely employed in high-energy physics. A potential, more environment-friendly, substitute for this gas is Tetrafluoropropene (HFO) and several promising HFO-based mixtures have been proposed. The long-term behavior (aging) of RPCs operated with these mixtures is typically studied by exposing several detectors flushed with an HFO-based gas mixture to a radioactive source and by studying the stability of the absorbed current and RPC performance over time. Experimental tests are crucial to spot and quantify aging effects, but can rarely provide an explanation for their origin. This requires a deeper understanding of the microscopical modifications of the materials induced by the HFO decomposition when exposed to irradiation. This project aims at breaking down the aging phenomena of several RPC components in their basic building blocks by comparing the chemical (EDX spectroscopy and SEM analyses) and electrical (resistivity) features of new and aged samples of RPC materials. The results of these analyses will be used to formulate a model to describe the observed effects and develop a simulation code, allowing for a systematic test of the aging properties of different HFO-based gas mixtures.

I will carry out my research at the High Voltage Laboratory of the ETH Zurich University and at the Physics Department at the University of Torino, with the guidance of Prof. Christian Franck and Martino Gagliardi, leading experts on eco-friendly high-voltage gaseous insulation and RPC detectors respectively, while the chemical analyses will be performed at the CERN chemical laboratory.

The data coming from these measurements will be saved and made publicly available in Zenodo, following the FAIR principles. The data analysis code will be developed using open source software and it will also be shared in a GitHub repository, to ensure analysis reproducibility and external verification of the results.

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EcoRPCchem

Data Summary

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?

The project does not foresee the re-usage of existing data. It does, however, include the study of some samples obtained by a particle detector that has been exposed to some irradiation in the past few years (aged samples in the following).

These materials have not been studied yet, so no data is available on them. Moreover, there are no third-party rights on these samples since I personally worked on them in the past and my current research group has accepted the proposal for these new studies.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

MACRO TYPE	TYPE	FORMAT (ONGOING)	FORMAT (PRESERVATION)	EXPECTED SIZE	SOFTWARE NEEDED?
TEXTUAL	Reports	.doc	.pdf	<10 MB	NO
	Raw spectra	.txt /.dat	.txt/dat	<10 MB	NO
	Current data	.txt /.dat	.txt/dat	~1 MB	NO
IMAGES	SEM images	.jpeg/.tif	.jpeg/.tif	~1 GB	NO
LASER MICROSCOPE	2D surface profiles	.vk4	.jpeg/.pdf	~10 GB	YES
CODE	Data analysis codes	.C/.cpp/.py	.C/.cpp/.py	< 500 kB	NO

Chemical analyses (performed by me at the ScopeM center at ETH)

- Two different chemical analyses will be performed:
 - Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDS) to study the abundance of elements in a sample
 - Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) measurements to provide visual magnification of the samples
- The output data from the EDS will be a two column file where the first column represents the energy of the impinging particle while the second represents the intensity of the material response to the specific energy
- The second column will be plotted against the first, leading to the creation of several response **spectra**
- Each energy is related to a specific element and the intensity of the response is related to its concentration in the sample
- The SEM provides high-quality and high-magnification images of the tested samples for visual inspection studies
- A legend for the fields in the files and a README file will be provided for each dataset

Electrical analyses (performed by me at the ETH High Voltage Laboratory)

- The output data from the electrical analyses is a value of circulating current as a function of time
- Two columns: current and time

- Knowing the voltage applied by the instrument one can measure the resistivity and conductivity of the material under test

Laser microscope

- These data refer to surface roughness measurements of the samples and they are saved in a proprietary format which can, nonetheless, be analyzed using the [vk4-python-driver](#) python library (developed by other users, hence not all the functionalities of the proprietary software are available)
- A pc with the license for the official program is available at ETH and it will be used to analyze the data

Different sources of aging (performed by me at ETH)

- After characterizing the brand-new materials these will be aged in two different ways
 - **Material compatibility:** the materials will be exposed to a given gas mixture and the simple chemical reactivity between gas and material will be studied
 - **Plasma-induced aging:** the materials will be exposed to the same gas mixture and this time the gas will be ionized using a plasma source and the effect of bombardment with electrons and ions will be studied

Methodology

The analyses will be carried out on different slabs and on different samples (different spatial regions on each slab). The slabs numbered 1 to 6 are the "virgin" samples (1,2,3,4,5 all come from the same Bakelite sheet while 6 is from a different one) while slab 7 and 8 are the ones already coming from previous aging studies. More specifically:

- Slabs 1-2: "old" Bakelite no linseed oil (material compatibility and plasma-assisted aging)
- Slabs 3-4-5: "old" Bakelite with linseed oil (material compatibility and plasma-assisted aging)
- Slab 6: "new" Bakelite with linseed oil (comparison with the samples coming from "aged" detector)
- Slab 7: anode of aged RPC detector
- Slab 8: cathode of aged RPC detector
- Slab 9-10: "old" Bakelite, no linseed oil for reference measurements of PDC

Different sample size is required for the chemical and electrical analyses. In general, more than one sample per slab can be obtained and more slabs will be subjected to the same aging in order to accumulate some statistics for the data analysis.

Moreover, some samples from a slab are used as reference and other samples from the same slab are used for the exposure and the measurements after the aging.

File naming scheme is as follows:

And a similar structure will be used for all samples. A dedicated database is maintained in order to easily associate each sample to its "origin" and different type of aging. One can notice that, for some samples, only the PDC measurement is foreseen; this is because the size of the sample needed for this measurement is much larger than what is needed for the SEM analyses so the samples are only used for PDC.

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Not applicable.

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

See the Table reported in Section 1.2

There are no costs foreseen for data storage as every record is < 50GB.

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

The data will be generated by me, using the instruments of the High Voltage Laboratory or the ScopeM laboratory at ETH.

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Data will be useful to the whole community of researchers using Resistive Plate Chambers (RPCs) as well as to other scientists interested in material compatibility and aging studies with the new, eco-friendly, gas alternatives.

FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

I have created a community in Zenodo to share publicly the data (<https://zenodo.org/communities/ecorpcchem>). Each record in Zenodo get its own DOI ensuring findability.

I have created a repository in GitHub to share the open source code developed to carry out the data analysis (<https://github.com/lucaquaglia15/EcoRPCchem>). Although GitHub itself does not provide a DOI for the code, one can use Zenodo to archive a repository on GitHub and issue a DOI for the archive.

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Examples of metadata from the discipline

- Date and time of the measurements
- Instrument type and measuring conditions (lens used, image resolution, detector used, scale, pressure, field of view, tilt)

Examples of metadata created by myself (scheme will be deposited in FAIRsharing)

- Legend and labels in the spectra
- Name of the samples and their origin/treatment/storage conditions
- Search keywords

Different machines will be used by the lab to perform the chemical analyses:

- Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM), equipped with Schottky field emission gun (FEG) ETD, LFD, GSED for Secondary Electron, BSDE, GAD for backscattered electrons and EDAC Octane Super for Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX)
- Software: FEI Maps, Ametek-EDAX TEAM, OIM, Genesis
- Focused Ion Beam (FIB)/SEM Zeiss XB540 with Secondary Electron Secondary Ion (SESI), Energy Selective Backscattered (ESB) and Back Scattered Detector (BSD) detector.
- KEYENCE laser microscope from VK-X3000 series

For what concerns the **electrical characterization** of the samples, the following will be used:

- An apparatus to measure the polarization-depolarization currents flowing through the materials and, using the ASTM D257-14 and IEC 62631-3-2 standards, it allows the computation of both the surface and the bulk resistivity of the sample

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Appropriate search keywords will be provided in the metadata, a detailed research of a controlled dictionary is ongoing on [FAIRsharing](#).

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Zenodo allows harvesting via OAI-PMH protocol.

2.2. Making data accessible - Repository: Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

The data will be deposited in Zenodo. This repository is managed by CERN and OpenAIRE, and it is well-known within the scientific community, and connects with many other tools within the open science ecosystem such as ORCID and GitHub. It is also non-profit and fulfills the qualitative conditions set by various funders.

Zenodo is trusted by OpenAIRE because the data will be stored safely for the future in CERN's Data Centre for as long as CERN exists (see Section 4.4).

2.2. Making data accessible - Repository: Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

Several arrangements have been explored and eventually the choice landed upon Zenodo, whose FAIR policies can be found [here](#).

2.2. Making data accessible - Repository: Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

According to [policy of Zenodo](#):

- (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
 - A DOI is issued to every published record on Zenodo
 - The DOI is a top-level and a mandatory field in the metadata of each record

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

The project will work according to the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary". Raw spectra, PDC data and laser microscopy images will be made immediately available on Zenodo. Other types of data will be made available as soon as the analysis is completed and validated.

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Not applicable.

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

According to the Zenodo policy:

- The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
 - OAI-PMH and REST are open, free and universal protocols for information retrieval on the web
 - Metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name.

- Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

No restriction will be applied.

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

Not applicable.

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Not applicable.

2.2. Making data accessible - Metadata:

Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

A CC0 licence will be associated to the data in Zenodo.

Reuse should be credited as follows: [Dataset name, created by Luca Quaglia, available at [DOI], date accession]

2.2. Making data accessible - Metadata:

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

According to the [policy of Zenodo](#):

- Data and metadata will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.
- Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available
 - Metadata are stored in high-availability database servers at CERN, which are separate to the data itself.

2.2. Making data accessible - Metadata:

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Open source code (developed in C++ or Python) will be freely available and uploaded to a GitHub repository. This has been created and it is available at this link (<https://github.com/lucaquaglia15/EcoRPCchem>)

2.3. Making data interoperable:

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

The project will follow the standards in use in the Physical science community, while having a strong link with chemistry, material science and electrical engineering. [FAIRsharing](#) registry will be explored to find suitable, community used ontologies and vocabularies to improve interoperability.

It will be carried out in the context of the DRD1 international collaboration (which also includes the participation of CERN) under the guidance of expert researchers already working with the mentioned instruments who can inform the researcher on the best practices usually adopted in the field.

2.3. Making data interoperable:

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

FAIRsharing registry will be browsed to find a suitable ontology, converging on the most widely adopted by the community.

2.3. Making data interoperable:

Will your data include qualified references [\[1\]](#) to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

[\[1\]](#) A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

At this stage no specific reference database is used.

During the analysis phase, if relevant, reference databases will be cited in this section.

2.4. Increase data re-use:

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

I plan to add a README file to my GitHub repository to explain how the developed code works and how it can be used to produce the output data.

I will upload a yearly report of the activities carried out on my Zenodo community. These reports will be fully accessible and they will automatically get a DOI attached to them.

I will upload all the presentations/conference papers of all the talks that will be given to international conferences and/or workshops regarding the project.

The methodology of the project has already been deposited in my community in Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12352743>) and the code repository has been created in Github (<https://github.com/lucaquaglia15/EcoRPCchem>)

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

All the data will be freely available in the Zenodo project community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/ecorpcchem>) with a CC0 license to maximize reuse.

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

There will be no restriction.

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

The [PROV standard](#) from the W3C consortium will be applied to enable other researchers to know who is the creator of the data (this information will also be included in the "creator" metadata in Zenodo).

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

A complete, streamlined protocol will be deposited in the Zenodo project community. **A summary of the main data-taking steps is reported here:**

- Samples are acquired by the researcher and are stored in a controlled environment (controlled temperature and humidity) in order to not alter their original features
- Whenever the samples need to be transported to the lab for analysis, they will be packaged carefully (e.g. using protective foil such as silk paper) and shipped with special instructions.
- Samples may need to be cut to a certain size, this will be done using a dry guillotine in order to avoid external pollution contamination
- Sample preparation is carried out under the supervision of experts in the lab
- Before carrying out the measurements, a detailed discussion with the laboratory will be carried out in order to maximize the outcome of each measurement and to not waste materials

The ETH laboratories applies the following quality standards :

- [ISO/TS 21383:2021](#), for what concerns the *qualification of the scanning electron microscope for quantitative measurements*
- [ISO 16700:2016](#), for what concerns the *guidelines for calibrating image magnification*

Data validation procedure :

- Data will be collected by myself and a report with the interpretation of the results will be created
- This is discussed in the research group and if something is not clear, help from the experts at the microscopy lab can be asked
- Peer review with other scientists can also be considered

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

See section Other research outputs.

Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

Open-source codes used for data analysis (which will be developed mainly in C++ and Python). Samples of detector components, following the various project phases, will be stored in a controlled environment for the whole duration of the project and can be provided/re-used for further studies/analysis.

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient

detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

Open-source code, developed for data analysis, will be uploaded a public repository on GitHub and a README file will be provided as documentation.

Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?

Due to the nature/size of the data/research outputs, no cost is foreseen to make them FAIR. In case. Nevertheless, in-kind support is provided from the Open Science Unit from the University of Torino (main partner of the project) to cover possible costs to make data and/or other research outputs FAIR

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)

If any significant change to the data, leading to a cost to make them FAIR, were to appear during project completion, the latter will be inserted in the project budget and would be eligible for reimbursement.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

The data manager of the project is Dr. Luca Quaglia, identified by ORCID 0000-0002-0793-8275. A support for the Data Management Plan is offered in kind by the Open Science Unit at the University of Turin (Dr. Elena Giglia, ORCID ID 0000-0003-4927-2623).

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository (as stated in [the Zenodo policies](#)). This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental program defined for the next 20 years at least.

Data files and metadata are backed up nightly and replicated into multiple copies in the online system.

All data files are stored along with a MD5 checksum of the file content. Files are regularly checked against their checksums to assure that file content remains constant.

Data security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

No security issue are foreseen due to the nature of the data and the project.

Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

No ethic or legal issues are foreseen due to the nature of the data and the project.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Not applicable.

Other issues

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

The project will be carried out at ETH Zurich. The institute has its own data repository, called "Research Collection" where researchers are encouraged to upload their data but this is not mandatory so I am not planning on uploading the data there.

The ETH repository has the same features as Zenodo.